

Current-Voltage Characteristics of Hydrogenated a: Si Thin Film Solar Cells: An Analytical Approach

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ABSTRACT

An analytical model has been developed for J-V characteristics of a-Si-H p-i-n solar cells. The model is based on the perturbation theory. The developed model provides more computational efficiency as well as better physical insight.

KEYWORDS: a-Si-H thin film Solar cell, Analytical current-voltage characteristics, Photo-generated Current Density, Dark Saturation Current Density, Exponential photon absorption.

1. INTRODUCTION

The second generation thin film solar cells draws increasing interest of the researchers because of their lower production cost and improved efficiency. Hydrogenated amorphous Si (a-Si:H) absorber based cells are one of the most potential photoconductors for thin film solar cells because of their excellent efficiency [1]. These solar cells use p-i-n type structure where the p and n-layers are few nm and the i-layer is $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$ thick. The incident photons are mainly absorbed in the i-layer and the photo-generated carriers are collected by the built-in electric field in this layer. The voltage-dependent charge collection in the intrinsic absorber layer is the dominant charge collection mechanism in thin film solar cells [4].

Till to date a few theoretical models [4, 5] have been proposed in the literature to describe the current-voltage characteristics of a-Si:H-based thin film solar cells. Hegedus *et. al.* [3] have shown in their work that the most successful model calculates the photocurrent by considering carrier drift and utilizing Hecht collection efficiency formula in the nearly intrinsic absorber layer. But their model [4] is based on an unrealistic assumption that all the carriers are generated at the top interface of the absorber layer for all incident photons. This model also used a number of fitting parameters which includes maximum photocurrent with complete charge collection, reverse saturation current, effective attenuation constant, series resistance and carrier ranges and hence, limited the applicability of the model. Mannan *et. al.* [5] developed an analytical

expression for the external voltage dependent photocurrent by considering exponential photon absorption, exponential electron-hole pair generation throughout the absorber layer, carrier trapping and carrier drift in the absorber layer. Although they derived an analytical expression for photocurrent in the absorber layer, they used numerical approaches to derive the J-V characteristics and used carrier ranges and series resistance as fitting parameters.

This work aims to analytically derive the J-V characteristics. In doing so the concept of the perturbation theory has been utilized. The model considered the absorber layer as lightly doped i-layer and hence, uniform electric field can be assumed to exist throughout the absorber layer. The voltage drop across the series resistance is calculated using the doping levels. Therefore, the proposed approach needs no fitting parameters.

2. ANALYSIS

The net current density of a solar cell can be expressed as

$$J(V) = J_d(V) - J_{ph}(V) \quad (1)$$

where $J_d(V)$ is the the dark saturation current density and $J_{ph}(V)$ is the photo-generated current density. Since the heavily-doped n and p-layers are very thin and the intrinsic base (a-Si:H) region is relatively wider, J_{ph} can be approximated as the photo-generated current component in the i-layer only. The voltage-dependent electric field throughout this region can be assumed as constant and can be expressed as

$$E(V) = \frac{V_{bi} - (V - JR_s)}{W_d} \quad (2)$$

where W_d is the width of the intrinsic layer. Unlike the work [5], this work uses V_{bi} instead of the fitting parameter V_0 . In Ref. [5], the voltage drop across the intrinsic layer JR_s is calculated from a measured

value of R_s . In this work, JR_s is calculated using the following expression

$$J(V)R_s = J(V) \int_0^{W_d} \frac{1}{q\mu_n n(x) + q\mu_p N_a} dx \quad (3)$$

where symbols have their usual meanings.

2.1. Derivation of Photo-Generated Current Density

The photogeneration current in the i-layer is the sum of the photogenerated electron current (J_n) and hole current (J_p). Since electric field is the dominant mechanism for current conduction in the i-layer, diffusion component of these currents are negligible. The basic equations required to deduce these drift-dominated currents are:

$$J_n = -qn\mu_n E \quad (4)$$

$$J_p = -qp\mu_p E \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{dJ_n}{dx} = \frac{qn}{\tau_n} - qG \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{dJ_p}{dx} = -\frac{qp}{\tau_p} + qG \quad (7)$$

where μ_n (μ_p) is the electron (hole) mobility, τ_n (τ_p) is the electron (hole) lifetime, the negative signs in Eqns. (4, 5) are due to the negative direction of the electric field E given by Eqn. (2) and G is the wavelength-dependent optical generation rate given by

$$G = \alpha(\lambda) \frac{I(\lambda)\lambda}{hc} e^{-\alpha_1(\lambda)W_B} e^{-\alpha(\lambda)x} \\ = \alpha(\lambda)G_0 e^{-\alpha(\lambda)x} \quad (8)$$

where α_1 is the absorption coefficient of silicon emitter layer. Combining the above equations [Eqns. (4) and (6) and Eqns. (5) and (7)] results in first order differential equations of electrons and holes as

$$\frac{dn}{dx} + M_n n = G_n \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{dp}{dx} - M_p p = -G_p \quad (10)$$

where $M_n = \frac{1}{\mu_n \tau_n E}$, $G_n = \frac{G}{\mu_n E}$ and

$M_p = \frac{1}{\mu_p \tau_p E}$, $G_p = \frac{G}{\mu_p E}$. Since the hole and electron start drifting immediately after generation

i.e. $n(W_B) \approx 0$ and $p(W_B + W_d) \approx 0$, the solutions of the electron and holes are obtained as

$$n(x) = n_0 (e^{-\alpha x} - e^{-M_n x}) \quad (11)$$

$$p(x) = p_0 (e^{-\alpha x} - e^{M_p(x-W_d)-\alpha W_d}) \quad (12)$$

where

$$n_0 = \frac{\alpha G_0 e^{-\alpha W_B}}{(M_n - \alpha)\mu_p E}$$

$$p_0 = \frac{\alpha G_0 e^{-\alpha W_B}}{(M_p + \alpha)\mu_p E}$$

According to [5], the electron and hole current densities in the i-layer can be expressed as

$$J_n(V, \lambda) = \frac{q\mu_n E}{W_d} \int_{W_B}^{W_B+W_d} n(x) dx \\ = \frac{\alpha q G_0 e^{-\alpha W_B}}{(\alpha - M_n)W_d} (J_0 + J_{n1}) \quad (13)$$

$$J_p(V, \lambda) = \frac{q\mu_p E}{W_d} \int_{W_B}^{W_B+W_d} p(x) dx \\ = -\frac{\alpha q G_0 e^{-\alpha W_B}}{W_d(M_p + \alpha)} (J_0 - J_{p1}) \quad (14)$$

where

$$J_0 = \frac{1}{\alpha} e^{-\alpha W_B} (1 - e^{-\alpha W_d})$$

$$J_{n1} = \frac{1}{M_n} e^{-M_n W_B} (e^{-M_n W_d} - 1)$$

$$J_{p1} = \frac{1}{M_p} e^{M_p(W_B - W_d) - \alpha W_d} (e^{M_p W_d} - 1)$$

The total photogenerated current J_{ph0} at a particular wavelength λ then can be expressed as

$$J_{ph0}(V, \lambda) = J_n(V, \lambda) + J_p(V, \lambda) \quad (15)$$

The total photogenerated current density is obtained by integrating over all incident photon wavelengths of the solar spectra, i.e.

$$J_{ph}(V) = \int_0^{\infty} J_{ph0}(V, \lambda) d\lambda \quad (16)$$

2.2. Derivation of Dark Current Density

Since the recombination current dominates over the diffusion current, the dark current density J_d can be approximated as the forward biased recombination current density in the i-layer and can be expressed as [5]

$$J_d(V) = \frac{qn_i W_d}{2\sqrt{\tau_n \tau_p}} e^{\frac{q(V-JR_s)}{AKT}} \quad (17)$$

where A is the diode ideality factor. In Ref. [5], A is used as a fitting parameter. In this work, the actual value of $A = 2$ is used. Therefore, this work does not need to use any fitting parameters.

2.3. Analytical Derivation of Total Current Density

From Eqns. (2) and (17), it is evident that determination of the total current density, J for a given load voltage, V is analytically intractable. However, using the concept of perturbation theory this intractability problem can be resolved. Since J_{ph} can be solved and $J_d \rightarrow 0$ under short circuit condition (i.e. $V=0$), the total current density J can be approximated as J_{ph} when $V = 0$. This is not the case for $V \neq 0$, where J_d is required and hence, in turn, the knowledge of J is required to determine the voltage drop across the series resistance R_s [Eqns. (2) and (17)]. Using the concept of perturbation theory, the JR_s at $V = 0$ can be used to determine at $V = \delta V$.

This is justifiable, since the change in $n(x)$ and $p(x)$ compared to N_a is negligible [Eqn. (3)] and hence, the change in current densities can also be negligible, provided that the change in the voltage is very little i.e. $\delta V \rightarrow 0$.

Therefore, the $n(x)$, $p(x)$ and JR_s at $V = 0$ can be applied to readily determine the J_d and E and hence, the total current density J at $V = \delta V$ using Eqns. (2) and (17). The same process can be repeated at the $V = 2\delta V, 3\delta V, 4\delta V, \dots$ where the values of n , p and J at $V = \delta V, 2\delta V, 3\delta V, \dots$ respectively are used. Therefore, for each δV

increment of voltage, J can be analytically determined.

Since the proposed approach needs no fitting parameters, it is more advantageous than the conventional numerical models. Therefore, the approach can provide better physical insight in the J-V characteristics. Although apparently similar to the numerical modeling approaches, the proposed approach is quite different. In the proposed approach, the total current density at any voltage level (V) can be determined only when the same at $V - \delta V$ is known. The number of iteration in the proposed approach, therefore, is limited to the size of δV . Therefore, the approach is expected to be computationally more efficient.

3. RESULTS

Following the analytical procedure outlined in the previous section and using the air mass (AM) 1.5 global spectrum from the ASTM G-173-03 standard [6] as the incident photon flux $I_0(\lambda)$, the J-V characteristics of a-Si:H p-i-n solar cells is plotted and analyzed in this work. The absorption coefficient for amorphous silicon is obtained from the absorption curves in Ref. [7]. The i-layer thickness is $2 \mu m$.

Fig. 1 shows the J-V characteristics for different sun intensities (100%, 32% and 10% of 1.5 AM global spectrum). J-V curves in this plot improve when intensity level is higher, since increase in the intensity level increases the photo-generated current and hence the short-circuit current I_{SC} .

Fig. 1: Net current density versus voltage at three sun intensities.

Fig. 2 shows that increase in the width of the intrinsic layer increases I_{SC} whereas the same decreases the open circuit voltage V_{OC} . When the width increases the optical absorption increases. This results in

increased photo-generation and hence the short-circuit current. Again, increase in width increases the series bulk resistance which results in a corresponding reduction in the open-circuit voltage. Fig. 3 shows that increase in the hole lifetime-mobility product increases I_{SC} keeping V_{OC} almost constant, whereas Fig. 4 shows that the increase in the electron lifetime-mobility product increases V_{OC} keeping I_{SC} almost constant. This indicates that the former has an effect similar to that of the series resistance and the later has the effect similar to the shunt resistance. Moreover, a comparison between these plots reveal that the J-V characteristics is more sensitive to the hole transport than to the electron transport.

Fig. 2: Theoretical net current density versus voltage for various level of $\mu_n\tau_n$ product of electron in a-Si solar cells.

Fig. 3: Theoretical net current density versus voltage for various level of $\mu_p\tau_p$ product of hole in a-Si solar cells.

4. CONCLUSION

An analytical approach has been developed to deduce the J-V characteristics of a-Si:H thin film solar cells having intrinsic absorber layer. It is expected that the proposed approach is computationally more efficient and offers better physical insight than the conventional numerical approaches available in the literature.

Fig. 4: Theoretical net current density versus voltage for various width in a-Si solar cells.

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Analytical Modeling of Internal Quantum Efficiency of CIGS Solar Cell

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ABSTRACT

In this paper an analytical model for the internal quantum efficiency is developed for the CIGS based Solar Cell. In doing so a uniform electric field has been assumed in the depletion region. The developed model shows that this proposed model can provide a better physical insight for Internal Quantum Efficiency for CIGS solar cells.

KEY WORDS: Thin film Solar Cell, Heterojunction Cells, CIGS, Internal Quantum Efficiency, Absorption Coefficient.

1. INTRODUCTION

The second-generation thin film solar cells are increasingly promising for their cheaper production and better efficiency. $CuIn_{1-x}Ga_xSe_2$ (CIGS) based cell is one of the most potential photoconductors for thin film solar cells because of its excellent efficiency [1]. The subscript x represents the mole fraction. The CIGS based solar cells have a substrate device structure of grid /ZnO /CdS /CIGS/Mo/glass [2][3]. The CIGS based cells are p-n heterojunction cells, where a very thin layer (50 μ m) of CdS acts as a highly doped n-layer and CIGS layer acts as lightly doped p-type absorber layer [4]. The thickness of the p-layer is 3000 μ m. The voltage dependent charge collection in the depleted absorber layer is the dominant charge collection mechanisms in thin film solar cells [3][5].

Internal Quantum Efficiency η is one of the most important factors of a solar cell because the efficiency of the solar cells is still limited; for example, commercial panels and terrestrial energy conversion, the efficiency is approximately 10% and up to 24% respectively [6]. The physics can be described by modeling the η accurately. So, various researchers have been working on the accurate modeling of η considering various effects. For CIGS based solar cells, Gloeckler [7] describes the device physics. Johansson [8] developed a numerical model of CIGS cell based on one diode model, whereas Gloeckler [9] derived a numerical model using AMPS Modeling. But these works did not develop an analytical model of η for CIGS solar cells.

In this work, an analytical model of η is developed for CIGS based solar cells and also observed the

change of η with changing in lifetime and doping concentration.

2. ANALYSIS

2.1 Basic Equations

The hole current density, J_p within the depletion region is given as:

$$J_p = qp(x)\mu_p(x)E_p(x) - qD_p(x)\frac{dp(x)}{dx} \quad (1)$$

where μ_p and D_p are hole mobility and hole diffusivity respectively. The Current continuity equation is given by :

$$\frac{dJ_p}{dx} = -q(R - G) \quad (2)$$

The electron current density, J_n within the depletion region is given as:

$$J_n = qn(x)\mu_n(x)E_n(x) + qD_n(x)\frac{dn(x)}{dx} \quad (3)$$

where μ_n and D_n are electron mobility and electron diffusivity respectively. The Current continuity equation is given by :

$$\frac{dJ_n}{dx} = q(R - G) \quad (4)$$

R-G is the net recombination rate.

2.2 Physical Models

2.2.1 Recombination-Generation

As we consider low doping, only SRH recombination will be present in our model. Therefore, from current continuity equation we get

$$\frac{dJ_p}{dx} = -q\frac{P}{\tau_p} + q\alpha G_0 e^{-\alpha x} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{dJ_n}{dx} = q\frac{n}{\tau_n} - q\alpha G_0 e^{-\alpha x} \quad (6)$$

2.3 Boundary Conditions

Boundary condition for depletion region are given as below:

1. for electrons at $x = W_E + W_d$;

$$n(W_E + W_d) = \frac{n_i^2}{N_A} \quad (7)$$